

OST

Eastern Switzerland
University of Applied Sciences

Successfully teaching digital competences to older adults.

Tips and recommendations for course providers.

Digital skills and competences are indispensable nowadays. Numerous courses support and promote these. This factsheet provides recommendations for Swiss course providers in the field of teaching digital competences to people aged 50+.

What is it about?

This factsheet provides recommendations for course providers in the field of teaching digital competences to people aged 50+. The recommendations are based on the results of the research project called "Digital skills and training needs of people aged 50+" (short: Digital skills 50+), conducted by the Institute for Ageing Research at the Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences, OST.

The research project was accompanied and advised by an advisory board consisting of members from Pro Senectute St. Gallen, Innovage, Swisscom, klubschule MIGROS and AvantAge. The project was funded from 2020 to 2024 as part of the National Research Program "Digital Transformation" (NRP 77) by the Swiss National Science Foundation. One aim of the research project was to support course providers in designing their offers for older adults (in this case: people aged 50+) in Switzerland in such a way that they meet the needs and preferences of their target group as well as possible. The following aspects of the research project are particularly central to the following recommendations:

- Real online courses offered by official continuing education institutions from all over Switzerland were considered for the study
- All course offerings that could be assigned to at least one of the following thematic areas of digital competence were considered: i) Basics and Access ii) Search, Evaluate, Manage and Store, iii) Communicate, Collaborate and Participate, iv) Create and Design, v) Security, vi) Problem-solving and Acting, vii) Analyse and Reflect
- Course experiences of participants
- Criticism, needs and open wishes for future courses from course participants

In the public discourse on digital skills and competences, there is often a comparison between "digital natives" and "digital immigrants". The existing heterogeneity(ies), i.e. differences, within the group of people over 50+ are rarely addressed. However, to design courses in the field of digital competences in such

a way that they meet the needs and preferences of different groups of older people aged 50+, a more differentiated approach is needed.

Tips & recommendations for course design

The self-assessment tool "Fit in the digital world: Digital competence 50 Plus" was developed during the pro-

ject so that courses can be tailored to and designed for the desired target group. Here, people interested in courses can classify themselves and thus find suitable courses for themselves. Based on the results of the research project, there are the following tips and recommendations for course providers.

It is recommended that providers...

- **increasingly offer courses aimed at older people with low to intermediate digital skills and competences.** Often the courses are either for absolute beginners or more advanced users. For example, not only courses that build on each other should be offered, but also self-contained courses.
- **tailor course descriptions more precisely to the desired target group.** This makes it easier for potential participants to identify the course as suitable for them. For example, by specifically mentioning that a course is for people aged 50 years and over, or for example for 70 to 85-year-olds, a course for women only, a course for older adults who own an Android smartphone, a course on photo editing on a smartphone, etc.

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Assessment Tool (self-assessment)

The assessment test gives you the opportunity to check your digital skills and identify potential weaknesses.

- **publish course offerings via various analogue and digital media and channels.** Flyers, brochures, radio advertising or similar. Make the offer easier to find and more accessible for the desired target group.
- **consider different areas of digital skills and competences in the course design.** Particularly in the areas of “problem solving” and “creating digital content”, older adults have a rather low average level of digital skills. Courses should be dedicated to a specific topic: security, communication or one of the general skills areas.
- **design courses in such a way that the focus is not only on teaching digital competences.** Factors such as participants’ healthy self-confidence in their ability to overcome challenges in general or a general interest in digital technologies also go hand in hand with a higher level of digital skills. The creation of an open learning culture, raising awareness of age stereotypes in relation to digital technologies and the use of positive age images can support this.

Based on the experience of course participants aged 50+, the following recommendations and tips on course design have been drawn up.

It is recommended that providers...

- provide digital and analogue teaching materials that participants can also access after the course.
- use “competent course instructors” who, in addition to professional competence, also have sound didactic knowledge and experience in teaching.
- ensure an appropriate balance

between the specific target group (e.g., 65 to 80-year-olds) and a good mix of course participants. In this way, there is sufficient room for different backgrounds and perspectives to be incorporated into the course despite the uniform group basis.

- Create opportunities for participants to meet on site for the course as well as after the course to promote the social component of courses more strongly.

About the “Digital skills 50+” project

The four-year research project “Digital skills and training needs of people aged 50+” focused on people in the second half of life in Switzerland. The focus was on people who have often acquired digital skills “on the job” and are not so-called “digital natives” (Prensky, 2001). In the first step of the research project, an overview of the existing online courses in the field of digital skills and competences in Switzerland was recorded. Further, the content of the identified courses was analysed and the experiences of older adults who had taken part in at least one course in the past were recorded. In addition to qualitative interviews with older adults, written surveys were also conducted on digital skills and course experiences and needs. The main objectives of the research project were to record the digital skills and continuing education needs, as well as the needs and preferences regarding the design of continuing education courses of people aged 50 years and over. Further information on the research project can be found at Hämmerle et al. (2022).

The research project “Digital Competencies 50+” of the IAF Institute for Ageing Research of the Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences is concerned with recording the digital skills and training needs of people aged 50+ in Switzerland. Among other things, the research project aims to build a bridge between course providers and those requesting digital training courses for 50+.

Digital participation in vocational education and training

It is not only older people who are confronted with the challenges of digitalization. People with disabilities of all ages are often forgotten when decisions are made in this area. The e-Inclusion project is investigating the opportunities and risks of digitalization for people with disabilities in vocational education and training. The project is also part of the NRP77 Digital Transformation research program. Further information can be found at inclusion-digital.ch.

Publications related to the research project "Digital Competencies 50+"

- Kortmann, L. K., Speck, S., & Wallimann, M. (forthcoming): Unpacking Digital Competences in Older Adults in Switzerland: Patterns and Predictors.
- Speck, S., Ruther, L., & Misoch, S. (2023). Digital Participation Among People Aged 50+ in Switzerland: Insights to Course Offers and Training Experiences. In Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies for Ageing Well and e-Health (pp. 48-58). <https://doi.org/10.5220/0011851900003476>
- Hämmerle, V., Reiner, J., Ruf, E., Lehmann, S., & Misoch, S. (2022): Beyond the Digital Divide: Digital Skills and Training Needs of Persons 50+. In Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies for Ageing Well and e-Health (pp. 276-282). <https://doi.org/10.5220/0011068200003188>

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